

“Baburnama” is the first encyclopedic dictionary

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Abstract. “Baburnama” is the masterpiece of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. Scientists have found that 28,000 words are used in this work, and it attracts the attention of many researchers. Although many scientists have worked on this work, there are still some unexplored issues. This can be an example of a thesaurus, which is one of the current problems in the field of linguistics. In this article, some of these words are explained scientifically as a thesaurus. In the process of creating a thesaurus of the work, we can success many new scientific achievements in computer linguistics.

Key words: Thesaurus, personal names, place names, turban, recitation, concubine, court, computer linguistics, commander, hierarchy, memoir.

Language is the main means of preserving and enriching our spiritual heritage. Researching classic works, determining the scientific, spiritual and educational value of written sources, studying the features of artistic language are among the urgent issues of the field of philology. We have the opportunity not only to get acquainted with all the scientific-historical and literary works created by the Turkic nations, but also to study within the field of Turkology. Among them, the works of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, in particular, the deep implementation of “Baburnama” and the creation of his thesaurus are among such works.

Researching and translating of “Baburnama” began in the XV century, when the work was created. until now, there are more than ten manuscripts of “Baburnama”, translations and publications were made in base of these manuscripts. “Baburnama” was translated 4 times into Persian and English, 2 times into German, French, Turkish, Urdu, 1 time into Dutch, Italian, Indian, Japanese, Polish, Spanish, Uighur, Kazakh. In the XIX century we can point to the works of, N. Ilminsky (1857), A. Vambéry (1964), W. Erskine (1826), and Turkish scientists such as Beveridge (1905-1921), N. Samoylovish (1917) as an example.

In Central Asia, Babur’s life and work have been recorded in dozens of creatures despite the fact that, on a new scientific basis, from the works of Yakubov, M. Shaykhzada, V. Zahidov in the articles and collections of prof. Fitrat, it continues seriously until now. Researching of the language features of “Baburnama”, in particular, the grammatical structure, began in the second half of the XXI century.

The great work “Baburnama” brought him world fame, and this work included the development of issues more than his “Devon”, “Mubayyin’ or “Aruz Risola”. is significant with the influence of the Persian language and literature in Khorasan, Movarunnahr, India, Afghanistan, Iran and Turkey in the XV-XVI centuries can be known through “Baburnama”. By its own decision, “Baburnama” is a historical-memoir work, with important historical events and the names of hundreds of historical figures. Information about some of these anthropotonyms are not often found in other historical works. Scientists has surprised with its uniqueness and important wealth of this work. In this work, the information about the status of the head of state and the leadership of the historical figures are shown, valuable information is provided in a multifaceted interpretation . While analyzing each historical figure and his activity, the author only examines their personality, character, attitude towards people and family members, character, reputation among the people, positive and negative sides.[1,56] Selects and interprets the most important aspects. In this respect, this work can be considered as a thesaurus. First, let’s clarify the term “thesaurus”. “Thesaurus” is derived from the Greek language and means “treasure”. Thesaurus refers to dictionaries that provide complete information on a specific field. Thesaurus has several advantages over monolingual dictionaries. Because, in it, a certain word is covered in every way. With its help, along with receiving complete information about the word in electronic form, our time is also saved. Thesaurus dictionary reveals the synonym, antonym, etymology, homonym of each word and a series of words that can be combined with it. A thesaurus is primarily a maximally complete dictionary in which words and examples of their use in the text are explained. They are mainly created in electronic form and are a means of detailed description of the field of certain subjects.

Recently, thesauruses are provided with hyperlinks for the convenience of the user. In the dictionary-article dedicated to the term “thesaurus” listed in Wikipedia, which is a virtual encyclopedia, the hierarchy of semantic relations and associative links is clearly visible. This memoir contains the names of several historical figures. and description is given. For example, in the work, Babur writes about his father Umarshaikh Mirza: **His birth and genealogy**. He was born in Samarkand in 860 (1455). He was the fourth son of Sultan Abusaid Mirza. He was younger than Sultan Ahmed Mirza, Sultan Muhammad Mirza and Sultan Mahmud Mirza. Appearance: he was a short man with a round beard and a sallow face. He wore a very tight coat. So much so that when tying a belt, he would pull his stomach in and tie it, and if he let go after tying it, the ties would often break. It was bad to wear and eat. The turban was wrapped by a dastorpech (a special turban weaver).

In those days, turbans were the whole thing. They didn't pull it flat, but let the end hang down. In the summer, he wore a Mongolian burqa in places other than the court[2;46].

Character: He was a man of pure faith in the Hanafi sect. He would not leave the prayer for five hours. His life had fully completed his daily prayers. Hazrat Khwaja was a disciple of Ubaidullah. He was a frequent visitor to his conversations. He had good literacy. He used to read “Hamsatayn” (Hamsa by Nizami Ganjavi and Amir Khisrav Dehlavi), epics and histories. He often read Shahnama. He has a poetic talent, but he was not diligent in writing poetry. His justice was such that under the mountains on the eastern side of Andijan, a caravan of a thousand cattle coming from China was covered in such snow that only two people escaped.Battles and wars. He fought three times. First, with Yunus Khan, in a place called Takasekretku on the banks of the Sayhun River, on the north side of Andijan.Sultan Ahmed Mirza was once again defeated in a battle between Shahruhiya and Oratepa, in a city called Khavas[3,78].

Provinces: His father gave him the province of Fergana. Several times, Tashkent and Sayram were under Mirza’s control. These cities were given to him by his brother Sultan Ahmad Mirzober. Shahrukhia was taken by fraud and used for a long time. **Descendants:** Mirza has three sons and five daughters. I am Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, the eldest of Bari’s sons. My mother is Kutlug Nigorkhan. Another son Jahangir was two years younger than Mirzomen. His mother, Fatima Sultan, was the daughter of one of the district governors of the Mongols. Another son was Nasir Mirzabo, his mother was a gunchachi named Umid from Andijan; he was four years younger than me. The eldest of the daughters, Khanzodabegim, was born from the same mother as me, she was five years older than me. When I took Samarkand for the second time, I went out with a person like Shaibani Khan in Saripul, we did not make mistakes in our zeal and enthusiasm as much as possible (it will be written about it in due time), but I was defeated and held the fortress for five months. We did not allow any deficiency in maintaining the fortress, strengthening it and leadership. The surrounding kings and begs did not give any help, I lost my spirit and left the city, the mother of one daughter, Ruqiya Sultanbegim, was Makhdum Sultanbegim, who was called Karakozbegim. ...**Amirs:** Khudoyberdi Temurtash. He is a descendant of the uncle of Herat governor Okbugabek. When Sultan Abusaid Mirza Jogi besieged Mirza in Shahruhiya, he gave the province of Ferghana to Umarshaikh Mirza and appointed Khudoyberdi Temurtosh as the governor. At that time, Khudoyberdi Temurtash was twenty-five years old, although he was young, his order, management and work behavior were

very good. A couple of years later, when Ibrahim Bekchik attacked the surroundings of Osh, Khudayberdi Temurtash took part in the war and was martyred... Another one was Khoja Husaynbek, a man and a poor man. According to the picture of that time, he sings songs well at parties... «Baburnama». is another example of a thesaurus. Because it contains valuable information about the trees, plants, grass, and flowers that grow in the mountainous regions from Ferghana to India.

Banana is one of the fruits of Hindustan. Arabs call it "mawz". The tree is not very tall, but it cannot even be called a tree. Something between a plant and a tree. The leaf is similar to the leaf of the marigold, but the length of the keila leaf is two inches, from the middle of the leaf comes a branch like a heart, the bud is on this branch, and the big bud is shaped like a sheep's heart, each bud is when the leaf opens, a row of six-seven flowers can be seen at the base of the leaf, and this row of flowers turns into a calyx. As this heart-shaped branch grows longer, the leaves of that big bud open and a row of cayla flowers appear. Each keila tree bears fruit only once. Keyla has two good features: one is that the skin peels off easily, and the other is that it does not have seeds and fibers, it is slightly longer and thinner than eggplant, and it is not very sweet. But Byangola keilas are very sweet. There is a very nice tree. Its broad, bright green leaves look beautiful. Another tree of Hindustan is taar. Taar's branches also grow only on top. They tie a pitcher like a date to the taar and drink its water. This water is called taari. This water is stronger than date water. On the branches of the taar is a single leaf up to half an old place after that, at the tip of the branch, thirty to forty leaves spread out in a bunch like a big paw. The length of these leaves is close to a centipede. A Hindu writes a letter on these leaves as if writing in a notebook. Also, Hindustani people, if they do not have rings in the wide holes of their ears, they make rings from this leaf and hang them. They make rings from this taar leaf to wear in the ears and sell them in the markets. Its body is better and straighter than that of a palm tree. Another bird common in Hindustan is the locha. It is also called a buffalo. Five or six different colors from head to tail. His neck is like a pigeon's. It is the size of a kabki river (as big as a mountain), perhaps it is a river like Hindustan. Because the kabki river lives in the highest places of the mountains, it also lives on the mountain tops. This bird lives in the Nijrov mountains of Kabul province and in the mountains below. It does not occur above it. The Hindustani people narrated an interesting story: when winter came, they used to get down on their toads: if they flew them over the vineyard, then they would not be able to fly at all, so they caught them. The meat is very sweet and considered halal.

In India, there are only animals that are unique to that place. One of the wild animals is the elephant. Hindustani people call it “haati”, it is in the borders of Kalpi province. Above it, wild elephants are more common as you go to the East. They bring elephants from those places. Thirty-forty people of Kurara and Manikpur are engaged in elephant hunting. The locals are responsible for every elephant before the government court. Elephant is a huge and intelligent animal. He understands what they say and does what he orders. The price is determined according to the size, it is sold according to the height. The bigger the elephant, the higher the price. They say that on some islands there are elephants that are ten years old. We did not meet any elephants taller than four or five years old here. An elephant eats and drinks only with its trunk. Without Khartoum, he cannot live. Khartoum has two large teeth on both sides of his upper jaw. It can knock down walls and trees with the force of its teeth. Fighting and any work that requires force is done with these teeth. These teeth are called oj. These teeth are highly prized by Hindustanis. An elephant has no hair. The importance of the elephant is great for the people of India. Every group (division, unit, detachment) in the army is accompanied by several elephants. An elephant has some good features: it can easily carry a heavy load through large and fast-flowing waters. Three or four elephants easily pull a pot cart (cart loaded with balls) that is pulled by four hundred to five hundred people. However, an elephant needs to eat a lot. One elephant eats the food of two camels.

Wonderful flowers grow in India. One of them is jaasun. Some Hindus call it “gadhal”. It is a stem tree, not a weed. The body is slightly taller than the red rose bush, the color is lighter than the pomegranate flower, and the size of the red flower comes, but when the red flower opens after budding, it blooms only once; and when the jasun opens, another thin stalk grows out from the middle of its flower, and the flowers of this jasun open again. As a result, a unique diltartar flower appears. It looks very colorful and beautiful on the tree, it does not last long, it fades in a day. Four months in the rainy season is very good and open a lot, maybe most of the year. Even if there is so much, there is no smell Babur even observed the growth of 32-33 different types of tulips in one of the foothills of Kabul and wrote down information about some of them. The thesaurus of toponyms has particular importance in “Baburnama”. In the Movarounnahr, Kabul and Indian parts of the work, we get valuable information about place names, their nature, flora, orchards, animals and birds, and weather.

Thesaurus of toponyms: Another one is Marginon. In the west of Andijan. From Andijan, it is seven kilometers away. A good town, rich in blessings: pomegranates and apricots are abundant and good. Birnav is a pomegranate: large, they say, with

a slightly sweet apricot taste due to its sweetness. It can be placed above Samnon pomegranates. There is another type of apricot, the seeds of which are removed and the pulp is dried. Game birds are good, and white deer are found near the town. Most of the famous fighters in Samarkand and Bukhara are from Marginon. The author of “Hidaya” is from Rushdon, Marginon. Another is Isfara, located at the foot of the mountain. There are running waters, saffron gardens and kindergartens. It is in the south-west of Marginon. There is a nine-lane road between Marginon and Isfara.

There are many fruit trees, but mostly almond trees are planted in the gardens. All its people speak Sort and Persian. There is a large stone among the hills on the south side of Isfara, which is called ‘Sanginoiyina (mirror stone)’. It is about ten years long, sometimes as tall as a person, sometimes as low as a person's waist, and it reflects everything like a mirror. Isfara region consists of four sub-districts: Isfara, Vorukh, Sokh, and Hushyor. When Muhammad Shaybani Khan and Sultan Mahmud Khan injured Olacha Khan and took Tashkent , Shahrukhiya, I came to the Sokh and Hushyar foothills with this Shah.

In conclusion, this work of Babur has being attracted everyone’s attention for centuries. This work is a perfect dictionary and a great treasure like thesauruses

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